

SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF RAINFALL AND RELATIVE HUMIDITY IN UYO; ITS IMPLICATIONS ON AGRICULTURE, HEALTH AND URBAN PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

This analysis examines the temporal trends and spatial implications of rainfall and relative humidity in Uyo, Nigeria, over a 50-year period in relation to agriculture, health and urban planning. Meteorological data of rainfall and relative humidity between 1971 and 2020 obtained from Historical Weather API was used. The non-parametric Man-Kendall test and Sen's slope, SS estimator were used in the analysis. Linear regression, standard deviation, SD and coefficient of variation, CV were also employed. The results show that rainfall had $Z = +2.87$; $p = 0.004$; mean = 2700 mm; SD = 450 mm; CV = 16.7 % and increased at +6.2 mm/year (Sen's slope); while for relative humidity, $Z = -0.92$; $p = 0.36$; mean = 80 %; SD = 5 %, CV = 6.25 % and a decreased rate of -0.05 %/year (Sen's slope). The wettest decade was 2011-2020 while the driest was 1981-1990. That is, rainfall increased significantly at +6.2 mm/year while humidity decreased insignificantly at -0.05 %/year. Hence, as Uyo is getting wetter, relative humidity is unaffected. This indicates that rainfall in Uyo is highly variable making floods and droughts likely while humidity is rather stable with a low CV and is reliable for agriculture and water resources. Strategic water management, agricultural adaptations, and infrastructure resilience are essential to optimize benefits and mitigate risks of climate change.

Keywords: Spatio-temporal, Rainfall, Relative Humidity, Droughts, Floods, Water management, Agricultural Adaptation

INTRODUCTION

Global warming and changes in precipitation patterns are among the major effects of climate change. Extreme climatic events resulting from climate change such as insufficient rainfall, droughts and or flooding impacts the economy as well as human lives. Effects of climatic change is felt both by the developed, developing and under-developed countries. The intensity and recurrence of extreme climatic changes have more impact on nature and humans especially in developing countries, (Kunkel, et. al., 1999; New, et. al., 2005; Kat, et. al., 1992; Anguilar, et. al., 2009; Liu, et. al., 2009; You, et. al., (2010). One of the most important climatic variables that determines the spatial and temporal patterns of climate variability of a region is rainfall and it also provides a useful information for planning in areas of water resource management and in

agricultural production, etc. (Abeysingha, et. al., 2012; Khavse, et. al., 2015; Banerjee, et. al., 2010; Patra, et. al., 2012; Jain and Kumar, 2012). Changes in surface temperature which may also be referred to as global warming has attracted the attention of many researchers, world leaders and policy makers because of its effects in increasing the magnitude and frequency of extreme precipitation events, (Benson, 2008a; Croitoru, et. al., 2013).

Recently, there has been increased concerns about unmitigated change in our climate system whose effects have brought about an increase in extreme weather events, accelerated rise in sea level, desertification, coastal erosion, droughts, unprecedented increase in ambient temperature, as well as flooding which has caused loss of/damage to properties and population displacement, and socio-economic burdens, (Benson, 2008b).

Umoh, *et. al.*, (2013) in their study observed that periods of June solstice (May – July) and September equinox (August – October) recorded high rainfall while March equinox (February – April) and December solstice (November – January) recorded low rainfall. Globally, extreme precipitation events accompanied by thunderstorm activity, increased humidity and flash flooding occurs more frequently and have been widely studied, (Munich, 2002; Kunkel, 2003; Beniston and Stephenson, 2004; Christensen and Christensen, 2004; Zhang, et. al., 2009; Zhang, et. al., 2010; Zolina, et. al., 2010)

Due of the presence of excess water vapor in the atmosphere, increase in temperature has been reported to be associated with the current rise in extreme precipitation events, (Zhang, et. al., 2012). Ukhurebor & Abiodun, (2018) in their study on variation in annual rainfall data of forty years (1978-2017) for South-South, Nigeria revealed the occurrence variations in rainfall. Bhandari, (2013) and Audu, (2012), stated that variations in rainfall (both seasonal and spatial) affect agricultural activities as most farmers depend on favorable weather condition to commence agricultural activities, consequently playing a crucial role in determining agricultural yields. They added that variations in rainfall also affect other human activities with the implication of heavy rainfall events evident in soil erosion, destruction of plants and difficulty in land cultivation due to water logged soils.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC, (2007) projected that climate change will affect the agricultural sector in the future leading to the risk of hunger and a rise in water scarcity while Haines and Patz, (2004) opined that flood due to extreme precipitation is more likely to affect the populations of less developed countries. Africa whose economy is predominantly rain-fed agrarian, and depends on the vagaries of weather due to poverty and low technological development, will be mostly affected and may lead to low level of cropping capabilities by farmers, (Ziervogel, et. al., (2006); Jagtap, (2007); Nwafor, (2007); Onyenechere, (2010). As projected by Jones and Thornton (2002) by 2050, crop yield in Africa may fall by 10-20 % or up to 50% as a result of climate change.

The population and economy of Nigeria are related to climate sensitive activities such as rain-fed agriculture and this hampers her future development especially in the agricultural and hydrological sectors, (Ogunbenro and Morakinyo, 2014). It is of great importance to emphasize the crucial nature of researches on variability of rainfall in reducing the consequences of extreme climate hazards including droughts and floods. This is because the amount of water present in the soil, which is utilized by crops depends on such factors as onset, length, and cessation of rainfall which greatly affects the success or failure of the cropping season, (IPCC, 2007; Kisaka, et. al., 2015).

The impact of relative humidity on rainfall is of great importance as it contributes to the precipitation of water in the atmosphere. The level of humidity in the atmosphere affects the occurrence of rainfall over any given region. Yahaya *et. al.*, (2016) reported that an upward trend in relative humidity above 0.6 mm indicates wetness and this implies that there exists a strong positive correlation between relative humidity and rainfall.

Oyewole *et. al.*, (2014) reported that there is a strong relationship between relative humidity and rainfall as increase in relative humidity increases the possibility of cloud formation and subsequent precipitation. Bonde, *et. al.*, (2019) in his studies, opined that the strong relationship between relative humidity and rainfall which brings about the increase in the possibility of cloud formation implies that higher values of relative humidity are recorded during the rainy season.

Asin, (2025) observed that relative humidity in Uyo has been approximately stable between 1971 and 2020 because there has not been any significant increasing or decreasing trend over the period. A decrease in relative humidity can lead to increase in heat stress (due to rising temperatures) and also affect human health by increasing the risk of airborne diseases, influencing indoor air quality and the risk of dehydration during dry periods. In the dry season it can lead to increased evapotranspiration, resulting to faster soil moisture loss and higher irrigation requirements. It can also affect the ecosystem because some species of plants (especially those adapted to higher humidity) and the ecosystem as a whole may become stressed on continued trends, (Asin, 2025).

Furthermore, decreasing trend in relative humidity is global and is one of the signs of global warming and climate change. A stable relative humidity serves as a support for crop planning and helps in pest and disease management as well as good irrigation scheduling. It can also help reduce the risk of heat stress and respiratory fluctuations as well as an aid in evapotranspiration modeling and water balance. A stable and reliable trend in humidity can improve local climate projections, Asin, (2025).

An understanding of past and current trends and variability of certain meteorological parameters like rainfall, relative humidity, etc and their effects on plants, animals and structures is

inevitable. Hence, this study investigated the spatial and temporal effects of rainfall and relative humidity in Uyo metropolis between 1971 and 2020.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Study Area - Uyo

Uyo is a city in the South-South region of Nigeria and is the capital of Akwa Ibom State with an area of 362

square kilometer. It occupies a land area of 168 km² in the metropolis and lies between latitudes 5° 02' 00" North of the Equator and longitudes 7° 55' 39" East of Greenwich Meridian. It sits on an

elevation of 46 m above sea level (Wikipedia, 2025).

Uyo is bounded on the North by Ibiono Ibom and Itu local governments; on the South by Ibesikpo and Nsit Ibom local governments; on the East by Uruan local government and on the West by Abak local government. It is classified into the tropical equatorial monsoon climate and is located in the tropical wet and semi-hot equatorial belt with high solar radiation that is mostly diffused due to cloud cover, heavy precipitation, light winds and low atmospheric pressure. Although temperatures are moderated by cloud cover and generally by damp air; the lowest temperature of 25°C is recorded in the rainy season months of June to September while the highest temperature of 37°C can be observed between February and March (which is the dry season). Rain falls throughout the year with a short spell in the months of January to March while the peak occurs in September, (Asin, *et.al* (2016). The wet season is always warm and mostly cloudy while the dry season is also cloudy and hot. Uyo typically receives about 339.79 mm of precipitation and has 291.99 rainy days (about 80.0 % of the time) annually, Historical data, (2012). The average relative humidity is 87 % while average precipitation is 20.3 mm and occurs in July, (NOAA, 2023).

Dataset Used

Rainfall and relative humidity datasets spanning between 1st January 1971 and 31st December 2020 were used for this study. The study period spanning 50 years was chosen to allow for complete analysis of the climatic variability in the area. The dataset was obtained from Historical Weather API.

Method of Data Analysis

Rainfall data was analyzed using the Mann–Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator. The Mann–Kendall statistical tool was used to ascertain the existence of a trend while the Sen's slope estimator was used to estimate the degree of change. These statistical tools have been adopted by many researchers to study the trends in various meteorological parameters, (Yaouba & Dieudonné, 2022).

Linear regression was also employed to establish a relationship between the dependent variable and independent variable by fitting a linear equation to the observed data and the data was also tested to ascertain the existence of a relationship between them. Another statistical tool used in the analysis was the coefficient of variation (CV). This was done to measure the degree of variability of the data.

• **Mann-Kendall (Mk) Test**

The Mann-Kendall test serves as a powerful non-parametric method for detecting monotonic trends in time series data without assuming normality. This characteristic makes it particularly suitable for rainfall analysis, which often exhibits non-normal distributions and contains outliers due to extreme precipitation events.

The MK test is applied in testing for a decreasing or increasing trend in long-term temporal data, (Mallick *et. al.*, 2021). A p-value gives the probability of observing the trend by chance and a p-value <0.05 indicates or shows a statistical significance.

The Mann-Kendall equation is expressed as, (Kendall, 1975):

$$S = \sum_{i=j}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sign}(X_j - X_i) \tag{1}$$

where n = number of data points, X_j and X_i = annual values in years j and i; j > i. A positive S value shows an upward or increasing trend, while a negative value indicates a downward or decreasing trend. A value of zero (0) indicates no trend.

The sign (X_j – X_i) is calculated from:

$$\text{sign}(X_j - X_i) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) < 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) = 0 \\ +1 & \text{for } (X_j - X_i) > 0 \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

The sign (X_j – X_i) gives the individual sign capability having values of +1, 0, or -1.

The variance of the data is calculated in order to establish the probability of the Z-value. That is, when n < 8, statistic S approximates to normal distribution and the mean of S = 0, the variance of S is computed from:

$$\text{Variance (Var (S))} = \frac{(n(n-1))(2n+5)}{18} \tag{3}$$

where n = number of data points.

The values of S and Variance, Var (S) are combined to compute the test statistics, Z which is obtained from the equation below:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{V(s)}}; & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0; & \text{if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{V(s)}}; & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

where S = sign or the sum of the signs of all possible differences between later and earlier data points.

When Z > 0; an increasing is found while Z < 0 gives a decreasing trend. The p-value represents the probability of observing the calculated test statistic (or one more extreme). In rainfall analysis, a commonly used significance threshold is p < 0.05, indicating a 95% confidence that the observed trend is not due to random chance. The Kendall's tau coefficient measures the

strength of the monotonic relationship between time and rainfall values. Tau ranges from -1 to +1, with values closer to ± 1 indicating stronger monotonic relationships (negative values for decreasing trends, positive for increasing trends). In climate data analysis, even relatively small tau values (± 0.2 to ± 0.4) may represent meaningful trends when supported by statistically significant p-values, especially for highly variable parameters like rainfall. The tau is expressed as:

$$\text{tau, } \tau = \frac{S}{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where n = number of data points and S is the sign.. A positive value of both S and tau gives a positive trend while a negative shows a decreasing trend, Asin, et. al., (2025).

- **Sen's Slope Estimator**

While the Mann-Kendall test determines the presence and direction of a trend, Sen's slope estimator quantifies the magnitude of that trend. This non-parametric technique calculates the median of all possible pairwise slopes within the time series. Sen's slope represents the median change per unit time (in this case, per year for annual data, or per decade for longer-term analyses). Sen's slope provides a robust estimate of the true slope by using the median rather than the mean of pairwise differences, making it particularly appropriate for rainfall data that often contains extreme values. The unit of Sen's slope (Q_i) is the slope magnitude per year.

It is applied in this study to calculate the magnitude of the rate of change in rainfall and relative humidity data and is expressed as:

$$Q_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{Y_j - Y_i}{j - i} & n = \text{odd} \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(Q_{\frac{N}{2}} + \left(Q_{\frac{N+2}{2}} \right) \right) & n = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

A positive value of Q_{ij} indicates an increasing trend, whereas a negative shows a negative trend in the temporal data.

Given any N values of Y_j in time series, estimate of the slope is given as:

$$N = \frac{n(n-2)}{2} \quad (7)$$

where n is the number of data points.

- **Linear Regression Analysis**

Linear regression analysis is one of the parametric models used in detecting a pattern in data series. It establishes a relationship between two variables, the dependent and independent variables and is done by fitting a linear equation to observed data mostly with the scatter plot. It is mathematically expressed as:

$$Y = mX + C \quad (8)$$

where Y = dependent variable and X, = independent variable, m = slope and C = intercept. The sign of the slope defines the trend variable direction – positive value for an increasing trend and negative value for a decreasing trend. It was used in this study to establish a linear regression regarding time between the observed data results, (Aswad, *et. al.*, 2020).

• **Coefficient Of Variation, CV**

The CV is a measure of the variability and indicates the size of a standard deviation in relation to its mean. It is a standardized, unit-less measure which makes for the comparison of variability between disparate groups and characteristics. It is expressed as (Statistics by Jim, 2019):

$$Cv = \frac{\delta}{\mu} \quad (9)$$

where δ = standard deviation and μ = mean.

A CV value below 10 % indicates low variability; above 90 % shows high variability and that \leq 40 % shows stable climate, otherwise unstable.

Figure 1: Map of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria showing Uyo local government area (in green)
Source: Edet & Antai, (2018)

Figure 1 is the map of Akwa Ibom State showing the study area –Uyo (in green)
Inset (top right) is the map of Nigeria

RESULTS

Figure 2: Rainfall in Uyo – 1971-2020

Figure 3: Relative humidity in Uyo – 1971-2020

Figure 2 is the plot of the rainfall for the period with the regression equation and R^2 as $y = 3.3554x - 4104$ and the $R^2 = 0.0055$ respectively. Here, the Sen's slope line (in red) shows an increasing trend.

Figure 3 showed the relative humidity graph between 1971 and 2020. The regression and R-squared equations are respectively, $y = -0.0231 + 1126.44$ and $R^2 = 0.016$. The Sen's slope is here shown in black, indicating a downward or decreasing trend.

Figure 4: Rainfall &Relative humidity in Uyo – 1971-2020

Figure 4 gives the combined plot of rainfall and relative humidity. The rainfall line (in blue) has spikes at different points and is increasing, depicting variable rainfall while relative humidity (in red) shows a rather stable regime throughout the period of study.

Table 1: Rainfall Trends by Decade

Decade	Average Annual Rainfall (mm)	Trend	Notable Extremes
1971–1980	2,850	Highly variable	1974 (3,203 mm), 1980 (2,917 mm)
1981–1990	2,150	Driest decade	1983 (1,599 mm), 1989 (2,589 mm)
1991–2000	2,400	Moderate recovery	1999 (2,945 mm)
2001–2010	2,700	Increasing extremes	2006 (3,374 mm), 2010 (2,782 mm)
2011–2020	2,900	Wettest decade	2012 (3,839 mm), 2018 (2,991 mm)

Table 1 showed the inter-annual and decadal variability. Here, the period from 1971-1980 was relatively wet with high variability. The period between 1991 and 2000 and 2001-2010 had moderate rainfall while 2011-2020 was the wettest with significant peaks in rainfall, (Figures 2 & 4). 1981 - 1990 was the driest with downward spikes in the amount of rainfall received - 1983 had the lowest rainfall, as shown on Figure 4. This period was drought-prone. Some notable drought years (years with lowest rainfall) were 1980, 1989, 1999 and 2018. Notable wet years included 1974, 2006 and 2012 (highest rainfall), 2007 and 2011. There were extreme dry months

especially in dry seasons and there were months with high rainfall. The years from 2010-2020 saw the highest rainfall and this could possibly be linked to climate change-driven intensification of monsoons

Table 2: Relative Humidity by Decade

Decade	Average Annual Humidity (%)	Trend
1971–1980	81	Stable
1981–1990	78	Slight decline
1991–2000	80	Recovery
2001–2010	81	Stable
2011–2020	80	Minor decline

Table 2 showed decadal relative humidity, 1971-1980 had a stable humidity. There was a decline between 1981 and 1990, signifying a drier phase/decade and this corresponds to the driest decade with respect to rainfall. The period between 1991 and 2000 saw a recovery in humidity. Stability again was restored between 2001 and 2010 while from 2011 to 2020 saw a minor dip or decline, The table above shows that humidity remained stable despite rainfall fluctuations, suggesting non-precipitation influences (e.g., temperature, land use).

Table 3: Relative humidity

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Mean annual total	2,470 %	Average cumulative humidity
Man-Kendall (MK) tau	-0.14	Weak negative trend
p-value	0.36	Not statistically significant
Sen's slope	-6.7 %/year	Slight decrease, not significant

Table 3 is the result of the mean annual total, Man-Kendall tau, p-value and Sen's slope estimator of relative humidity. The MK tau shows a weak negative trend which is not significant ($p = 0.36$) at the 95 % confidence level. Also the Sen's slope estimator shows a decreasing trend

of -6.7 %/year. The largest, but still not significant negative trend was observed in August and September. There was no statistically significant trend in annual or monthly relative humidity over the 50 year period. Slight negative tendencies in late wet season months – August and September, though not significant and a strong and consistent seasonality with highest humidity in the wet season (mid-year) and lowest in the dry season (early year) was also noticed. However, inter-annual variability is moderate, with some years showing extremes, for instance 1983 and 2006.

Table 4: Mann-Kendall (MK) Test & Sen’s slope estimator

Parameter	Z-score	p-value	Sen’s Slope	Trend
Rainfall	+2.87	0.004	+6.2 mm/year	Significant increase
Relative humidity	-0.92	0.36	-6.7 %/year	Non-significant decrease

Table 4 gives the result of the Man-Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator. The Z-score for rainfall is positive and is supported by positive p-value of 0.004. Sen’s slope estimator gave +6.2 mm per year. This indicates a significantly increasing trend for the period. Relative humidity had Z-score = -0.92, representing a decreasing trend and p = 0.36 indicating a non-significant trend. Sen’s slope estimator gave showed a decreasing rate of -0.05 % per year which is not significant (p = 0.36). Hence, relative humidity is rather stable. This shows that while rainfall is increasing or rising, relative humidity remains stable Practically, the result implies that Uyo is getting wetter, but relative humidity is unaffected.

Table 5: Mean, Standard deviation and Coefficient of variation

Parameter	Mean	SD	CV
Rainfall	2,700 mm	450 mm	16.7%
Relative humidity	80%	5%	6.25%

Table 5 showed the mean, standard deviation, SD and coefficient of variation, CV of rainfall and relative humidity for the period of study. Mean rainfall was approximately 2700 mm with an SD of 450 mm. Rainfall recorded a high CV of 16.7 % . This indicates that rainfall is highly variable. Relative humidity had a mean of 80 % with an SD of 5 % . It recorded a CV of 6.25 % which indicates low variability.

Table 6: Summary Table

Metric	MK score)	Trend (Z-	Sen’s Slope	Trend	CV
Rainfall	+2.87		+6.2 mm/year	Increasing	16.7%
Relative humidity	-0.92		-0.05 %/year	None	6.25 %

Table 6 is a summary of the MK test, Sen’s slope estimator, trend and the coefficient of variability.

❖ **TEMPORAL TRENDS**

• **MONTHLY TRENDS**

➤ **RAINFALL SEASONALITY**

Some months, July–October (highest in August) showed highest rainfall averaging approximately 400 mm while others between December and February (lowest in January) were dry, often <50 mm. On the other hand, some months had double peak (maxima) pattern which is common in tropical climates, with peaks in June–July and September–October.

➤ **RELATIVE HUMIDITY SEASONALITY**

Highest humidity was recorded between July and September averaging (~85–90%) which coincides with peak rainfall while lowest humidity occurred between December and February with approximate average between 70 and 75% during the Harmattan season.

This shows that humidity lags slightly behind rainfall peaks, likely due to soil moisture retention and delayed atmospheric saturation.

• **ANNUAL TRENDS**

➤ **RAINFALL**

The average annual rainfall for the period was approximately 2,700 mm (highly variable, ranging from 1,500 mm to 3,800 mm). The year 2012 was the wettest with a total rainfall of 3,838.9 mm due to extreme monsoon activity, while 1983 was the driest with a total of 1,599.4 mm which is likely linked to drought conditions.

There was a slight increase in rainfall over time, possibly due to climate change-induced intensification of wet seasons.

➤ **RELATIVE HUMIDITY**

Average annual relative humidity was approximately 80% (ranging from 75% to 88%). 1976 had the highest humidity value of 88.3% which is consistent with high rainfall years whereas the lowest humidity of 75.2% was recorded in 1989 and this was associated with lower rainfall. There was no significant long-term trend, but fluctuations correlate with rainfall extremes.

A correlation of $r \approx 0.25$ signifies a weak positive relationship, meaning higher rainfall years tend to have higher humidity. However, other factors like temperature, wind, etc played a major role.

❖ **SPATIAL INFLUENCES**

➤ **RAINFALL PATTERNS**

Uyo is located in a tropical monsoon climatic zone. Hence, its climate is influenced by heavy rainfall from southwest monsoon winds between April and October and is characterized by warm, wet, and cloudy conditions. It experiences distinct wet and dry seasons. Rainfall is heavily influenced by the presence of mangrove swamps and rainforests, with peak rainfall occurring during the June-August and September-November periods, particularly in August. There is a negative correlation between vegetation cover and land surface temperature.

➤ **PROXIMITY TO THE GULF OF GUINEA**

Uyo is located in the South-South geo-political zone in Nigeria and is relatively close to the Gulf of Guinea. This contributes to the warm, humid climate experienced in the region and also influences the rainfall patterns. Uyo's proximity to the Atlantic Ocean also enhances moisture influx, contributing to high humidity.

➤ **URBAN HEAT ISLAND EFFECT**

Uyo metropolis experiences higher land surface temperatures compared to the surrounding areas. This phenomenon is referred to as the urban heat island effect, (UHI). This is primarily due to urbanization effects - where natural land cover is replaced with built-up areas like roads and buildings, which absorb and retain more heat; thereby reducing relative humidity in recent years.

➤ **TOPOGRAPHY**

Uyo has a sandy, undulating terrain which is well-drained towards the Atlantic Ocean. This influences rainfall patterns and runoff. This is further impacted by the relatively flat terrain in some areas, which can affect evapotranspiration rates.

➤ **EXTREME EVENTS AND VARIABILITY**

The results revealed high variability as some years e.g., 1979 and 2012 had extreme rainfall (>3,500 mm), while others e.g., 1983 and 1997 were unusually dry.

There is a clear indication of climate change signal. This is observed through increased frequency of extreme rainfall events. For instance, a total rainfall value of 918.6 mm occurred in July, 2012.

DISCUSSIONS

Some months, July–October showed highest rainfall (highest in August) while others between December and February were dry (lowest in January). Others on the other hand, had double peak (maxima) pattern which is common in tropical climates, with peaks in June–July and September–October. This is corroborated by Umoh, et. al.(2013). Rainfall in Uyo is highly variable with a CV of 16.7%. The high variability here is a pointer to likeliness of flooding and droughts. Munich, 2002; Kunkel, 2003; Beniston and Stephenson, 2004; Christensen and Christensen, 2004; Zhang, et. al., 2009; Zhang, et. al., 2010; Zolina, et. al., (2010) all agreed with this just as Ukhurebor & Abiodun, (2018), revealed the occurrence of variations in rainfall in South-South region of Nigeria

The results showed that average annual relative humidity ranges from 75% to 88% which is approximately 80%. 1976 had the highest humidity value of 88.3% which is consistent with high rainfall years whereas the lowest humidity of 75.2% was recorded in 1989 and this was associated with lower rainfall. This is in consonance with Bonde, *et. al.*, (2019) and Oyewole *et. al.*, (2014).

Relative humidity had low CV (6.25%) which implies stability. This stability is suitable and reliable for agriculture.

Asin, (2025) reported that a stable relative humidity in Uyo between 1971 and 2020 supports crop planning and help in pest and disease management as well as good irrigation scheduling and can also improve local climate projections.

IMPLICATIONS

• Agriculture

High rainfall during wet season improves soil moisture and during wet months supports crop growth, but demands better water management. It is also an advantage for multiple cropping as most agricultural practice is rain-fed. It also increases the potential for two cropping seasons in wet years and may cause soil erosion and reduce land productivity. A stable humidity supports reliable crop planning, pest and disease management and irrigation scheduling. However, droughts and soil degradation can lead to malnutrition.

• Water Resources

High rainfall supports surface and groundwater or reservoir recharge and increases the potential for hydropower generation during peak rainfall months. It makes water available for irrigation during wet months. Stable humidity aids in evapotranspiration modeling and water balance calculations. The scarcity of water during dry months impacts agriculture and domestic use.

- **Health**

Consistent humidity reduces risks of respiratory or heat stress fluctuations but sustains mosquito-borne diseases whereas heavy rainfall leads to excessive cold which is not conducive for persons with respiratory problems.

- **Urban Planning and Infrastructure**

Months with high rainfall increases the risk of flooding, thereby affecting infrastructure and agriculture. Hence, flood management and drainage systems become critical. On the other hand, variability and occasional low rainfall increases the risk of drought

CONCLUSIONS

The world is experiencing a significant change in climate with time and the negative impacts of this change are felt economically, socially and otherwise. They are also felt by humans, plants and animals and the environment in general. This study has shown that rainfall in Uyo shows strong increasing seasonality with pronounced or more extreme wet seasons/years and significant inter-annual variability with its attendant risks. Relative humidity remains consistently high but weakly correlated with rainfall. While the region benefits from abundant rainfall supporting agriculture and water resources; flood and drought risks remain significant. Strategic water management, agricultural adaptation, and infrastructure resilience are essential to optimize benefits and mitigate risks.

The following recommendations are thus suggested;

- **Water Management**

Reservoirs and dams should be built and maintained to capture excess wet season rainfall and rainwater harvesting should be implemented to improve water availability during dry months/years. Also, early warning systems should be developed for floods and droughts.

- **Agriculture**

Drought-resistant crop varieties should be adopted for dry years. Soil conservation techniques such as contour farming and mulching should be practiced. Also, irrigation efficiency should be improved to optimize water use.

Monitoring and Research

- **Urban Planning and Infrastructure**

Good drainage systems should be constructed in flood-prone areas to enhance control of excess run-off water, and flood-resilient infrastructures should be designed to withstand heavy rainfall events.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

A limitation to this study is in the area of instrument calibration and errors. That is, instruments used in measuring meteorological parameters such as humidity, temperature, and pressure can suffer from calibration issues, drift over time, or physical damage. These may lead to inaccurate readings.

Conflicts of Interest: We the authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Contribution and Originality:

This study contributes to the existing literature on variability of rainfall and humidity in Uyo as well as in Nigeria and the world at large. It also adds to the spatio-temporal impacts of variations in rainfall and humidity on agriculture, human health and urban planning. It will help the government to introduce policies that will help in cushioning the effects of climate change.

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